

The Credit Channel and Monetary Policy During Pre- and Post-2008 Crisis: Evidence from Firm-Level Data in Korea

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ABSTRACT

We find that the relationship between monetary policy and corporate borrowing spreads changed during the global financial crisis. This relationship is only significantly positive after the global financial crisis, which means that the credit channel is effective in Korea. As for the corporate asset size classification, this is only significant after the global financial crisis. As for the corporate equity ratio attribution, the coefficient of monetary policy for low-equity ratio companies is significant after the global financial crisis. In contrast, the coefficient for high-equity ratio companies is only significant after the global financial crisis. In addition, after the global financial crisis, the contraction of US monetary policy had a positive impact on the borrowing spreads of domestic companies. Coincidentally, the relationship between the above structural spread and US monetary policy reversed before the global financial crisis.

KEYWORDS: biofertilizer, rabbit urine, neem cake, okra, Far North Cameroon.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the global financial crisis in 2008, governments have actively implemented monetary expansion policies to stabilize financial markets and prevent the deterioration of the real economy. In addition, developed countries have responded to the financial crisis by adopting measures such as unconventional monetary policies, including quantitative easing and forward guidance. Monetary authorities have long been running loose monetary policies intended to induce growth in the real economy and recover from the economic recession stemming from global financial crisis, but the results have not been ideal.

Traditional channels of monetary policy transmission include the money channel and the credit channel. However, the global financial crisis that erupted in 2008 has shaken the traditional operations of monetary policy. Following the crisis, there has been a renewed examination of the role played by banks and other financial intermediaries in the transmission of monetary policy, with the risk-taking channel of monetary

policy transmission emerging as a significant area of study Borio and Zhu (2012). Nevertheless, many studies still regard the credit channel as the fundamental conduit in the transmission of monetary policy, asserting that differences in financial market structures have not materially affected the importance of the credit channel (Ciccarelli et al., 2015). Even under zero interest rate policies, quantitative easing, or negative interest rate frameworks, the credit channel continues to play a substantial role in the transmission of monetary policy.

To prevent further economic downturns, major economies have adopted expansionary monetary policies such as increasing the supply of money and lowering interest rates to provide liquidity to the markets and reduce the financing costs for businesses, aiming to improve the financing environment and investments, and to foster economic recovery. Since the 2008 GFC the Federal Reserve reduced the federal funds rate to an ultra-low level of 0%–0.25%, close to the zero lower bound, leaving traditional monetary policy with no room for maneuver. To assess the stance of monetary policy, considering

the constraints of the zero lower bound, we utilize the shadow short rate calculated by Krippner (2013). Like other central banks, the Bank of Korea kept interest rates low to restore the real economy and stabilize financial markets after the GFC (Figure 1). Research indicates that while monetary policy played a crucial role during the outbreak of the financial crisis, its effectiveness has been gradually decreasing (Ma and Lin, 2016). This phenomenon is also observed in South Korea. Some authors have observed that since the 2008 financial crisis, the relationship between South Korea’s monetary policy and macroeconomic variables has weakened (Park and Choi, 2021), and its effectiveness has also declined Gang and Lee (2014) and Han and Hur (2020).

The purpose of this paper is to examine whether the monetary transmission mechanism has changed since the 2008/09 financial crisis. This study also seeks to determine the types of firms that act as a conduit for the transmission of monetary policy to the real economy. If this transmission works through high risk, bringing economic recovery in the short run can make it inherently unstable going forward by increasing the share of risk activity. In contrast, if low-risk firms and those in a good financial position are the main recipients of monetary policy in a downturn, not only can they increase output in the short term, but they can also decrease the level of risk in the long term.

Fig 1 The stance of monetary policy

Notes: The figure shows that the red line is the Bank of Korea (BOK) base rate, while the green line and blue dotted line is the Federal Funds Rate (US_FFR) and the shadow short rate (US_SSR).

Source: The Bank of Korea

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 summarizes in the literature. Section 3 describes the data and outlines our empirical methodology. We then present the empirical results in Section 4 and conclude the paper in Section 5.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Our paper makes two contributions to the literature. First, we provide support for the transmission of a credit channel for monetary policies. Monetary shocks to the real economy through credit channel is investigated. A credit channel functions as a set of factors that amplifies traditional monetary

transmission mechanisms. Numerous empirical studies of credit channels have conducted aggregate response analyses. Examples include Ashcraft and Campello (2007) and de Bondt (2004), who use proxy variables to assess the operability of the balance sheet channels in their papers. They examined several effects of balance sheets, such as the use of corporate bond spreads or gaps in GDP at the state level in the US. However, their analysis used aggregate data and thus could not take into account firm heterogeneity. On the other hand, Park and Lee (2017) use firm-level data to prove the effects of monetary policy on external financing premiums of Korean firms. It is important to note here that firms' external financing premiums were assessed using indirect indicator. Due to the scarcity of

data, studies which analyze borrowing spreads often use substitution variables or bank lending data to measure credit channels.

This paper measures firms' financing premiums directly, rather than using indirect variables. In South Korea, some studies such as Kim and Lee (2013) and Kim (2017) argue that monetary policy has been less effective since 2000, while other authors argue that it has remained effective. This line of research focuses on the effectiveness of the interest rate channel and the asset price channel. This paper attempts to fill this gap in the literature, finding that the effect of monetary policy on firms' borrowing spreads has changed after the recent GFC. In our sample, the result is a statistically significant positive relationship between the base interest rate and firms' financing spreads, which is consistent with credit channel theory and some empirical results (Aysun et al., 2018; Bounader and Doukali, 2019). Aysun et al. (2018) found that the U.S. monetary policy coefficient values can be positive or negative. One potential explanation for the different results by type and period could be firms' demand for and access to credit, and their deleveraging behavior. However, their core result is that a change of the monetary stance after the GFC of 2008/9 decreases the borrowing spread between high-risk firms and low-risk firms, a finding inconsistent with the core result of this paper.

Second, this paper studies the direct impact of monetary policy measures in other countries on domestic firms. Alper et al. (2020) found that foreign monetary policies (mainly in the United States, the United Kingdom and the Euro area) had an impact on the bank loans received by banks located in Turkey. Morais et al. (2019) show that the major countries' unconventional monetary policy (mainly in the United States, the United Kingdom and the Euro area) strategies have in expansionary effect in the Mexican banks' credit supply and inducing strong firm-level real effects. These research suggest that the effect of large countries' unconventional monetary policy strategies have in essence substantial spillover effects in emerging markets. It is because the supply of domestic credit is affected by foreign monetary policy shocks through foreign banks. Hence, we are keenly curious about whether such spillover effects would occur in South Korea. Recent studies related to the evaluation of unconventional monetary policy (UMP) develop different methods to identify unconventional monetary policies. Some of them use the central bank's balance sheet (Evangelos et al., 2017; Wang, 2019). The direct use of

changes in the size of central Banks' balance sheets to measure monetary policy is not without its problems, since it does not capture the prior announcement effects. This paper use the shadow short rate of Krippner (2013). They are calculated as latent variables and risk factors to predict the values of federal funds rate if it were to fall below zero. Our analysis confirms the existence of the effect of U.S. monetary policy on the borrowing spreads of domestic firms. This is consistent with the results of previous studies. It is important to note here we also found that this impact has changed between pre- and post-GFC period.

Finally, our study builds on the work of Aysun et al. (2018), who tested credit channels. Our analysis tests credit channel through the financial positions of firms. In addition, the difference here lies in how firms are classified, with empirical results pertaining specifically to the Korean economy. Our model also includes the impact of US monetary policy on domestic firms.

3. METHODOLOGY: DATA, DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS AND EMPIRICAL APPROACHES

3.1 Data and variables

We use 24,061 firm-year observations in Korea for the periods from 2000 to 2007 and 2010 to 2019. Our sample is restricted to those firms listed on the KOSPI and KOSDAQ stock exchanges, excluding financial firms (banks and insurance companies). The financial information of the sample firms is obtained from the KIS Value database, while the macro data are from the Bank of Korea and the site of Leo Krippner.

We construct firm-level borrowing costs based on Oh et al. (2011) and then subtract the risk-free rate, which is the firm-level borrowing spread (BS). To compute this variable, we use the rates on five-year Treasury bonds and the one-year Treasury bonds as our respective indicators of long-term and short-term risk-free interest rates. We measure the monetary policy of Korea using the Bank of Korea (BOK) base rate. It is expected that a lower value of the base rate would improve a firm's financial position by having a positive impact on the firm's borrowing spreads. We use the rates of the United States to measure the stance of foreign monetary policy. It is important to note here that unconventional monetary policy in the US spans from the fourth quarter of 2008 to the fourth quarter of 2016. Therefore, for the foreign monetary policy (US_FSSR), we use the federal funds rate data before the GFC and the shadow short rate data after the GFC. In addition, we measure

the output gap (GDP) as the real GDP minus the real potential GDP divided by the real potential GDP. We use three firm-level of independent variables. The leverage ratio (Lev) is the ratio of total debt to total assets. The liquidity ratio (Liq) is the ratio of current assets to total assets. The return on assets (ROA) is the ratio of net income to total assets. The descriptive statistics of the key variables are presented in Table 1.

In order to analyze the asymmetric sensitivity of firms' borrowing spreads to monetary policy changes depending on financial constraints, we measure two factors: the asset size (A) and the debt-to-equity ratio (DE). Indeed, the asset size has been widely used in existing empirical studies of financial constraints as they affect firms in Korea. Researchers have found that small firms are more sensitive to monetary policy (Park and Lee, 2017; Baak and Ryuk, 2018). Therefore, we classify firms in the top 10 percent of the firm's asset size distribution as large asset size firms (AT10%) and those in the bottom 10 percent as small asset size firms (AB10%). This is especially important because firms are divided according to internal financing and external financing according to the degree of financial friction. The larger the firm's assets are, the fewer financial constraints they face. Moreover, as in Lee

(2015), our analysis includes the debt-to-equity ratio as another criterion. Specifically, the firm can face instability and a high debt-to-equity ratio, increasing the risk of default or prompting the firm to depend more on external funding. Therefore, in this paper, adding the debt-to-equity ratio allows a more accurate identification of the types of firms and how they are affected by monetary policy. Firms in the top (DET10%) and bottom (DEB10%) 10 percent of the debt-to-equity ratio are used as high and low debt-to-equity ratio, respectively, in the analysis. Overall, in this paper, we study the following types of firms: large (AT10%), a low debt-to-equity ratio (DEB10%) as less riskier groups, and small (AB10%), and a high debt-to-equity ratio (DET10%) as more riskier groups.

Table 1 shows the various summary statistics of firms based on the partitioning criteria and for the two sample periods that we use in our analysis. The borrowing spread has increased for small asset size firms (AB10%) after the GFC. Conversely, the borrowing spread has decreased for low debt-to-equity ratio (DEB10%). Comparing the two sample periods we find that the leverage ratio is significantly reduced for each type of firm. These patterns suggest that risk differentiation became more evident after the GFC in Korean credit markets.

Table 1 Firm-level descriptive statistics

	AT10%	AB10%	DET10%	DEB10%
Before GFC				
BS	2.95	1.84	3.78	3.6
Leverage	56.22	57.02	82.85	18.35
Liquidity	32.47	55.43	46.76	53.72
ROA	4	1.21	-6.14	6.11
No. of firms	155	337	426	431
Observations	946	947	954	989
After GFC				
BS	1.93	3.84	3.59	2.96
Leverage	44.7	41.44	68.84	12.59
Liquidity	33.45	56.31	45.39	45.41
ROA	7.66	-2.03	1.58	3.24
No. of firms	225	465	500	548
Observations	1447	1447	1447	1449

Notes: Based on the BS variable, all firm-level continuous variables are winsorized at the 5% and 95% levels to mitigate the impact of outliers

3.2 Empirical approaches

Our approach has two main components: constructing firms' borrowing spread variables and investigating the impact of

monetary policies on this variable. We follow Oh et al. (2011) in which borrowing costs were constructed using the interest paid by the firm on debt in a given period divided by the debt, which includes all forms of firm financing.

$$\text{Borrowing cost} = \frac{\text{total Interest expenses}}{\text{average Interest-bearing liabilities}} \quad (1)$$

Here, the interest-bearing liabilities are the sum of short-term borrowing, the current portion of long-term liabilities, long-term and short-term bonds, long-term borrowing, long-term accounts payable - other, consolidated debt, and short- and long-term liquidity debt.

The firm borrowing spread (BS) is then the borrowing cost minus the risk-free interest rate. Because a firm’s debt includes long-term and short-term debt, the risk-free interest rate uses the short-term Treasury bond interest rate and long-term Treasury bond interest rate. To examine the borrowing spreads in relation to the impact of monetary policy, we develop a dynamic model. Our model builds on the work of Aysun et al. (2018).

$$BS_{i,t} = \beta^{bw} BS_{i,t-1} + \beta^{BOK} BOK_{t-1} + \beta^{US_FFFR} US_FSSR_{t-1} + \beta^Z Z_{i,t-1} + \beta^{GDP} GDP_{t-1} + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

In this equation, *i* refers to the sample firm and *t* is the year. $Z_{i,t-1}$ is a vector of the firm-specific variables, and $\epsilon_{i,t}$ is the error term. In our model, the primary focus is on the stance of the monetary policy, BOK_{t-1} , US_FSSR_{t-1} and on the firm's financial position, $Z_{i,t-1}$. The firm’s financial position can be expressed by different variables, and this paper sources those from Ono et al. (2016) that utilized three variables. These three variables include the leverage ratio, the liquidity ratio and the return on assets. In addition, the output gap is included to account for the cyclical behavior of credit markets.

We used an unbalanced panel data made up of different firms for the time periods 2000-2007 and 2010-2019. The GMM method is a widely used estimation method capable of producing consistent and more efficient estimates with dynamic panels. Our use of the GMM estimation methodology is based on the work of Arellano and Bond (1991), with the estimate calculated with equation (2). When using a lagged dependent variable as the independent variable, the unobserved panel-level fixed and random effects are correlated with the independent variables, making standard estimators inconsistent. We can use effective instrument variables to solve the

endogenous problem. This estimator assumes no residual autocorrelations. The conditions satisfy the hypothesis that first-differenced residuals have no autocorrelations or second-order autocorrelations. In addition, the Sargan test was used to verify the effectiveness of any over-identification.

4. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

4.1 Baseline results

Table 2 reports the baseline results of the monetary policy effect on the borrowing spreads. The Sargan p-value and AR (2) statistics indicate that our model well specified for all specifications. Before the GFC, our model indicates that lagged variable of borrowing spreads and leverage are important determinants of a firm's borrowing spread. Furthermore, the borrowing spread is not significantly affected by monetary policy changes. In contrast, after the GFC, the lagged variable of the borrowing spread, leverage, return on assets, and the output gap show significant effects.

We should note also that we have different results depending on the different periods. The relationship between monetary policy and a firm's borrowing spread is positive after the GFC. This implies that if the monetary policy rate decreases, firms’ borrowing spreads decrease. This positive relationship is consistent with typical theoretical predictions pertaining to the standard interest rate channel and credit channel (Bernanke et al., 1995; Bernanke et al., 1999). Considering that the borrowing spread consists of the borrowing cost minus the interest rate of Treasury bonds, one possible explanation of these results is that the interest rate channel and the credit channel work in Korea after the GFC. This positive relationship is consistent with some studies, such as Baak and Ryuk (2018) and Park and Lee (2017). The difference is that this mechanism operates in opposite direction before the GFC.

Turning to the other explanatory variables, the borrowing spreads are procyclical after GFC. Bernanke et al. (1999) point out that two opposing effects of output on borrowing spreads. Specifically, the heightened demand for investment and external finance by firms during an economic expansion tends to elevate borrowing spreads. Conversely, the increase in asset prices and net worth typically witnessed during such expansions exerts a dampening effect on borrowing spreads. Regarding the firm financial position, when the default probability of firms (Lev) decreases, the return on assets (ROA) decreases, and the liquidity (Liq) increases, the borrowing spread is reduced. The relationships between borrowing

spreads and the US monetary stance that are reversed when we consider the period before and after the GFC. Before the GFC the borrowing spreads are negatively related to the shadow rate and the corresponding relationship is positive after the GFC. We will discuss this further below.

4.2 *The effects of monetary policy and financial constraints on firms' borrowing spreads*

To test the impact of financial constraints on firms' borrowing spreads formally, we use the firm's assets and debt-to-equity ratio to classify firms. The main advantage of this classification method is that it allows a more accurate identification of the type of firm to which the monetary policy was transmitted.

Table 3 presents the results based on each type of firm's asset partition. The central finding in this table is that monetary policy transmission operates through the large asset size firms (AT10%) only after the GFC. Specifically, we assume a 1 percentage point decrease in the base rate in the last year, with borrowing spreads for large (AT10%) asset size firms in the current year then down by 0.823 percentage points. In contrast, it was not significant before the GFC. This result is inconsistent with Baak and Ryuk (2018) and Park and Lee (2017). They examine the validities of the credit channel among monetary policy transmission mechanism to confirm whether the monetary policy affect corporate premium and investment or not. They found that the relationships are statistically significant monetary policy in small- and medium and large-sized firms. These findings suggest that the monetary policy is in operation in the Korean corporate sector. Firstly, their classification of firms asset is different from our analysis. They define firms with assets of more than 500 billion won as large firms and those with assets of less than 500 billion won as small and medium-sized firms. Secondly, the variables of firm's borrowing cost that they use is proxy variable, and it's different from our analysis. Similarly, after the GFC, if the U.S. unconventional monetary policy rate would have decreased by one percent, the borrowing spread for the large asset size firms would have decreased by 0.255 percentage points. Conversely, before the GFC, in the U.S. unconventional monetary policy rate would have decreased by one percent, the borrowing spread for the large asset size firms would have increased by 0.219 percentage points. With respect to variables of the firm financial position, the leverage variables were significant before and after the GFC. The return on assets variable was significant only the small firms before the GFC. This suggests

that firms' financial position variables are less important determinants of borrowing spreads.

Table 4 presents the results based on each type of firm's debt-to-equity ratio partition. The central finding is that after GFC, the decrease in the monetary policy rates (monetary easing) decreased the borrowing costs of low debt-to-equity ratio firms that pay a low premium when borrowing. Conversely, the tight monetary policy stance before GFC increased the borrowing costs of high debt-to-equity ratio firms that usually pay a higher borrowing premium. We should note also that the coefficient is significant of unconventional monetary policy in the U.S.

According to the results of Table 3 and Table 4, we found that the effectiveness of monetary policy was different according to the financial frictions of firms. That is, the credit channel works through the high debt-to-equity firm's before the GFC. Conversely, after the GFC, the credit channel works for firms with large-sized and low debt-to-equity ratio. One possible explanation for our results is that after the GFC the loose monetary policy can increase output and increase the level of risky activities by low-risk (debt to equity ratio) and large-size (large asset) firms. Because large-size firms can manage their borrowing costs. That is, if BOK decreases the base rate, large firms can decrease more since they can use some collateral to lower interest rates. In case of low debt-to-equity firms, they are the similar case with large firms. Our analysis confirms the existence of the credit channel. Here, we find that the effects of credit channel on monetary transmission are different by the assets size and debt-equity ratio levels of firms. In addition, after the GFC, the coefficients of monetary policy in the United States were mostly statistically significant for all types of firms. We find that both domestic and foreign monetary policy coefficients are significantly positive. In contrast, the relationships between borrowing spreads and the US monetary policy stance that are mentioned above reversed before the GFC. We find that the relationship is negative and significant. One potential explanation for the results is that before the GFC the Fed raised the interest firms were reluctant to borrow more. For AT10% firms, they can borrow debts at a low interest rate (lower borrowing costs) even if the Fed increases the interest rate before the GFC. That is why there is negative coefficient before the GFC. For DET10% firms (high debt), their borrowing cost is already high. If the Fed raises the policy rate which is related to the risk-free interest rate, then the borrowing spread decreases. For the DEB10% firms (low debts), they are like large firms. Since they have small debts,

they can manage their borrowing costs effectively even if the Fed increases the policy rate. Overall, we find that the relationship between the US monetary policy and the borrowing spread of firms has changed before and after the GFC.

4.3 Robustness test

We re-estimate the baseline results using alternative monetary policy stance. Specifically, in the U.S we use the shadow short rate data before the GFC. The estimation results using the shadow short rate are presented in Table 5. Compared to the baseline case using the federal funds rate data as provided, the results are consistent with those of the baseline model. The coefficient for BOK is not significant, and foreign monetary policy stance (US_MS) is significantly negative for before the GFC.

We also test the robustness for our results on each type firm's asset and debt-to-equity ratio partition. We study the following types of firms: large (AT20%), a low debt-to-equity ratio (DEB20%) as less riskier groups, and small (AB20%), and a high debt-to-equity ratio (DET20%) as more riskier groups. We remain use the shadow short rate data in the U.S. Nevertheless, we find that before the GFC monetary policy transmission didn't operate in Korea. We also find that foreign monetary policy stance coefficient is mostly significantly negative.

5. CONCLUSION

A number of previous studies have been devoted to analyzing the effects of finance and monetary policy transmission on firms. However, there is still very little work in emerging markets, with most research focused on highly developed markets. Little is known about the relationship between firm finance and monetary policy transmission in emerging markets, particularly with firm-level data. The evidence provided by this analysis from the perspective of funding providers can be very useful for policymakers and researchers in their efforts to understand how different institutional settings and specific characteristics of firms lead to different policy conclusions.

We constructed a sample from the balance sheets of firms' annual reports, analyzed the relationship between firm financing characteristics and monetary policy in Korea before and after the GFC, and used the firms' characteristics to solve the heterogeneity problem. We use the GMM method to analyze this dynamic relationship in a single equation. The GMM method is a widely used dynamic panel estimation

method capable of estimating dynamic panels more consistently and effectively.

The results show that after the GFC, monetary policy has a significantly positive impact on firms' borrowing spreads across firm size distribution, which shows that since 2000, the impact of monetary policy has changed on firms' borrowing costs in Korea. Regarding firm debt-to-equity ratio partition the coefficient of monetary policy for the low debt-to-equity ratio firms is significant after the GFC. In contrast, the coefficient of the high debt-to-equity ratio firms is significant only before the GFC. Considering that the tightening of monetary policies is detrimental to the balance sheets of firms, such policies increase the borrowing spreads of firms. A statistically significant positive value implies that credit channel work in Korea. Overall, we find that the effects of credit channel on monetary transmission are different by the time periods, the assets size and debt-equity ratio levels of firms. Secondly, foreign monetary policy has a significant impact on domestic firm's borrowing spreads. For example, after the GFC, unconventional monetary policy stance of the US has been as sensitive. By contrast, before the GFC, the sensitivity was insignificant. Finally, after 2009, all type firms benefited from monetary easing except those with risky (high debt-to-asset ratios) firms. Our empirical results show that the credit channel is effective in Korea.

The findings of the paper also provide important implication for the policy transmission mechanism. After the GFC, the expansionary monetary policy reduces firms borrowing spread through cutting interest rates, while policy interest rate cuts to stimulate the economy through credit channels to achieve policy intentions. Second, while US policy rate reduces will reduce domestic firms borrowing spread. The expansionary monetary policy of the United States has the effect of stimulating the domestic economy through its influence on Korea's firm.

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Table 2 Baseline Estimation Results

	(2-1) 2000-2007	(2-2) 2010-2019
L1BS	0.166*** (6.589)	0.427*** (9.935)
L2BS	0.008 (0.582)	0.136*** (5.195)
L1BOK	0.163 (1.036)	0.877*** (5.875)
L1US_FSSR	-0.109*** (-2.788)	0.292*** (8.563)
L1GDP	0.000 (0.359)	0.001*** (2.709)
L1Lev	0.120*** (12.997)	0.056*** (9.454)
L1Liq	-0.004 (-0.489)	-0.004 (-0.663)
L1Roa	-0.002 (-0.384)	0.039*** (6.445)
Sargan test	0.079	0.063
AR(2) test	0.414	0.354
N	4494	6730

Note: Numbers in parentheses denote t statistics and the superscripts *, ** and *** represent significance within 10%, 5% and, 1% respectively. The sargan test and AR(2) test, which are p-value.

Table 3 The effect of firm size distribution

	(3-1)	(3-2)	(3-3)	(3-4)
	2000-2007		2010-2019	
	AT10%	AB10%	AT10%	AB10%
L1BS	0.271*** (5.498)	0.062 (0.995)	0.427*** (5.635)	-0.332** (-2.282)
L2BS	0.061** (2.446)	-0.019 (-0.426)	0.059 (1.504)	-0.223*** (-2.760)
L1BOK	-0.186 (-0.544)	0.075 (0.135)	0.823*** (3.893)	-0.680 (-1.118)
L1US_FSSR	-0.219*** (-3.109)	-0.202 (-1.020)	0.255*** (5.138)	0.178 (1.454)
L1GDP	0.003* (1.726)	-0.000 (-0.029)	0.001 (1.383)	-0.003 (-1.421)
L1Lev	0.084*** (5.116)	0.035* (1.886)	0.017* (1.925)	0.032*** (3.230)
L1Liq	0.070*** (3.211)	0.010 (0.579)	0.004 (0.311)	0.006 (0.490)
L1Roa	-0.012 (-0.575)	-0.033** (-2.576)	0.006 (0.594)	0.013 (1.454)
Sargan test	0.294	0.287	0.068	0.074
AR(2) test	0.439	0.197	0.358	0.430
N	490	203	659	302

Note: Numbers in parentheses denote t statistics and the superscripts *, ** and *** represent significance within 10%, 5% and, 1% respectively. The sargan test and AR(2) test, which are p-value.

Table 4 The effect of firm debt-to-equity ratio distribution

	(4-1)	(4-2)	(4-3)	(4-4)
	2000-2007		2010-2019	
	DET10%	DEB10%	DET10%	DEB10%
L1BS	0.092** (2.370)	-0.070 (-0.920)	0.106* (1.713)	0.161*** (2.642)
L2BS	-0.042 (-1.458)	-0.112** (-2.097)	-0.221*** (-6.372)	0.083* (1.893)
L1BOK	0.956** (2.298)	0.630 (0.753)	0.185 (0.648)	0.958*** (2.783)
L1US_FSSR	-0.304** (-2.418)	-0.484* (-1.830)	0.130** (2.012)	0.379*** (3.434)
L1GDP	-0.004 (-1.522)	0.002 (0.570)	0.001 (1.238)	0.001 (0.633)
L1Lev	0.118*** (3.184)	0.054 (0.672)	0.003 (0.317)	0.225*** (4.258)
L1Liq	0.036** (2.094)	-0.018 (-0.402)	-0.031** (-2.305)	0.018 (0.699)
L1Roa	-0.005 (-0.955)	0.039 (0.717)	0.004 (0.329)	0.062*** (2.897)
Sargan test	0.341	0.103	0.107	0.843
AR(2) test	0.962	0.225	0.164	0.077
N	113	134	254	242

Note: Numbers in parentheses denote t statistics and the superscripts *, ** and *** represent significance within 10%, 5% and, 1% respectively. The sargan test and AR(2) test, which are p-value.

Table 5 The effect of firm size and debt-to-equity ratio distribution

	(5-1)	(5-2)	(5-3)	(5-4)	(5-5)
	2000-2007	AT20%	AB20%	DET20%	DEB20%
L1BS	0.165*** (6.55)	0.301*** (8.14)	0.175** (2.67)	0.115 (1.87)	0.026 (0.35)
L2BS	0.008 (0.58)	0.016 (0.57)	0.008 (0.24)	-0.012 (-0.40)	-0.032 (-0.80)
L1BOK	0.124 (0.82)	0.083 (0.28)	0.446 (1.25)	0.553 (1.64)	-0.243 (-0.49)
L1US_SSR	-0.095** (-2.90)	-0.161** (-2.73)	-0.053 (-0.47)	-0.195** (-2.91)	-0.191 (-1.95)
L1GDP	0.0003 (0.39)	0.002 (0.99)	0.001 (0.17)	-0.003 (-1.46)	0.001 (0.30)
L1Lev	0.120*** (13.01)	0.121*** (6.21)	0.092*** (4.47)	0.136*** (5.26)	0.129** (2.92)
L1Liq	-0.004 (-0.47)	0.041* (2.38)	0.005 (0.34)	0.027 (1.44)	-0.010 (-0.35)
L1Roa	-0.002 (-0.38)	0.016 (0.77)	-0.013 (-1.24)	0.011 (1.49)	0.015 (0.51)
Sargan test	0.086	0.978	0.573	0.654	0.869
AR(2) test	0.414	0.466	0.790	0.984	0.402
N	4494	911	529	358	338

Note: Numbers in parentheses denote t statistics and the superscripts *, ** and *** represent significance within 10%, 5% and, 1% respectively. The sargan test and AR(2) test, which are p-value.